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School Characteristics and Students' Academic Performance in Chemistry in Public and Private Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study examined school characteristics and students' academic performance in Chemistry in public and private senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study evaluated the influence of teacher qualification and instructional material on students' academic performance in Chemistry. Descriptive survey research method was used in this study. Two research questions and two research hypotheses were used to guide the study. The sample size was three hundred and ninety (390) senior secondary (Chemistry) students in Rivers State. School Characteristics Inventory (SCI) (.80) and Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) (.75) were used for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze research questions and two-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the research hypotheses. From the findings of the study, teacher qualification (Df, 3 = 116.403, $P < 0.05$ and instructional materials (Df, 3 = 13.43, $P < 0.05$) significantly influenced students' academic performance in Chemistry. The study recommended that teachers should utilize the available opportunities to improve themselves with the current technological trends such as computers, internet and other electronic systems.

Keywords: School characteristics, students' academic performance, Chemistry, public and private senior secondary schools.